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BRAIN ULTRASOUND AS A DIAGNOSTIC AND FOLLOW UP METHOD OF LATERAL VENTRICLE DILATATION IN HOSPITALISED CHILDREN AT THE NEUROLOGY DEPARTMENT – PEDIATRIC CLINIC

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Abstract

A child's full development is tied closely to the full development of the human's central nervous system, which is why there are so many cases reported with central nervous system illnesses in children. Being very familiar with a child's normal development, a Pediatric Neurologist doctor is capable of noticing any sort of neurological deviation during the first month of child's development which can be backed up with diagnostic methods such as: Transfontanellare Ultrasonography which is the chosen method to diagnose such anomalies and also helps keep track of them.

Key words: Brain ultrasonography, ventriculomegaly, our clinical experience.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to analyze the speed in which these anomalies have as a main effect for the expansion of lateral ventricles that lead on to early stage of the brain damage.

Material and Methods

As a case study we had the children that were hospitalized at the Pediatric clinic the Neurological department between February 2015-April 2016. There were total of 410 children that were examined with the General Electric Ultrasound equipment with high frequencies probes from ranges of 6-8 MHz. All children underwent standard examination with 5 coronal and 5 sagittal planes. The ages included were from 1 month old to 12 months old children, with it being 230 female and 180 male subjects. From all these examinations there 26 cases diagnosed with ventriculomegaly from where they had to go into constant monitoring and had to undergo into examination with transfontanellar ultrasonography every 2 months, from all these cases there was only one case that developed into hydrocephalus, a medical record MRI was requested and was provided from a Radiologist which confirmed our diagnosis and with the ongoing consultations with neurosurgeon a ventricular-peritoneal shunt was applied and up until today the child’s medical condition is healthy, but still being under a neuro pediatricians surveillance.

February 2015- April 2016 / 1 month – 12 months	
230 female	180 male
<i>From all these, resulting 26 cases with ventriculomegaly, follow up was performed every two months with transfontanellar ultrasonography.</i>	

Results

From the deriving results at these children, we have managed to make an early diagnosis and multidisciplinary treatment, therefore the survival rate of children with central nervous system diseases has significantly improved.

Conclusion

Brain ultrasonography is a method with high priority in diagnosis of many central nervous system diseases, it is a noninvasive method that can be performed while the patients are still in bed, and dynamic changes of brain structure can be followed as well, with the only precondition that the child’s fontanelle must be still open.

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